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With focus on non-technical engineering skills

C. Lindholm

Associate professor
Department of Computer Science, Lund University
Lund, Sweden
E-mail: christin.lindholm@cs.lth.se

C. Nyberg

Associate professor
Department of Electrical and Information Technology, Lund University
Lund, Sweden
E-mail: christian.nyberg@eit.lth.se

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INTRODUCTION AND RELATED WORK

How can we prepare engineering students for their professional life? To have a successful career in engineering, the engineer needs both technical engineering skills and non-technical engineering skills. To systematically address non-technical engineering skills six mandatory Engineering days have been introduced at the Bachelor programs in Computer Engineering and in Electrical Engineering with automation at Lund University's campus in Helsingborg.

The ability to communicate, to work in teams, reason about ethical questions, have an understanding of entrepreneurship and economy are some of the non-technical engineering skills of interest. This has been recognised by certification bodies that have included such non-technical engineering skills in their demands on engineers. For example, to be accredited by the Accreditation Board for Engineering in the US, an engineering education program must show that their students can collaborate in multidisciplinary teams and can communicate effectively [1]. Also The European Union has stressed the importance of non-technical engineering skills and the inclusion of them in the curriculum of engineering education programs in the EU. The Dublin descriptors in the framework for qualifications of the European Higher Education Area include ethical and social issues. On a national level, several countries demand that non-technical engineering skills should be included in

engineering programs. For example, in 2012 the Swedish National Agency for Higher Education evaluated all Swedish engineering education programs. In that evaluation the non-technical engineering skills played an important role, and some programs were highly criticised and threatened with losing their right to graduate engineers because they failed to fulfil demands on non-technical engineering skills. Employers also underline that non-technical engineering skills are important [2]. The authors of this paper have similar experiences from focus group meetings held together with nine different companies situated in the south of Sweden. They all stressed out the importance of non-technical engineering skills in the employment process. Larsen et al. [3] have observed that it is not only technical knowledge that is needed for a successful career in engineering, but also non-technical engineering skills, for example being able to co-operate in multidisciplinary/multicultural teams, justify the value of new technical solutions and present an analysis to people with different background. A summer course developed at Aarhus University in Denmark in cooperation with the company Bang & Olufsen, was surveyed 2-6 years after the course and the result showed that the students experienced that the course gave them a more holistic view of product development and also improved their ability to work in heterogeneous groups.

Non-technical engineering skills such as oral and written communication, ethics, the impact of technology on society and group dynamics are introduced in engineering programs as compulsory courses used to cover non-technical engineering skills. The main contents of a course are either non-technical engineering skills as such or engineering with non-technical engineering skills as an integrated part. Some engineering programs offer their students non-technical engineering skills in non-compulsory activities like summer courses or other types of non-curricular activities. Knobbs and Grayson [4] describe how self-awareness, empathy, relationships, communication, group dynamics and conflict handling are introduced in a course in the third year of a mining engineering program. Reading assignments, peer interaction, coaching, psychometric tests, and work in heterogeneous groups were used during the course and the authors of the article claim that the papers the students write during the course and the course evaluations show that the students' non-technical engineering skills were increased. A concern, according to Cech [5] is that engineering students during their studies tend to become less concerned with public welfare, a claim that is backed by surveys from four American universities. Since engineering plays an increasingly larger role in our society, that may lead to serious problems the author emphasises. It is also noted by Herkert [6] that in 80 % of all engineering education programs in the USA, the students do not have to take any ethics-related courses. The author also surveys the ethics education for engineers in the USA and the most common way of introducing ethics is case studies, sometimes supplemented with ethical theories. There are two common approaches, a required course with elements of ethics or a cross-the-curriculum approach, where ethics are spread through the curriculum during the years.

Six mandatory Engineering days, called "Ing-dagar" have been developed in a project and introduced at the Bachelor programs. Approximately 80 new students are admitted to the two programs each year. The programs first year are very similar in content but year two and three differ significantly. This paper describes the project and ideas behind the concept "Ing-dagar" in section 1, the organisation and content of the concept in section 2 and in section 3 the observations and lessons learned. Some thoughts about future work will be given in section 4.

1 THE PROJECT AND IDEAS BEHIND

The project with four members (three teachers and one Coach ACC and Educational Coordinator) started out with thoughts about ethics, since in the Higher Education Ordinance (1993:100) there is a demand that the students must show the ability to make judgments with respect to relevant ethical issues. When different ways of implementing ethics were discussed, new ideas on other non-technical engineering skills started to grow. The knowledge and skills the students need to have as an engineer related to the Higher Education Ordinance and also what is required by industry were surveyed and the project was enlarged to embrace further non-technical engineering skills (described in section 2).

The members in the project defined four guiding principals for the concept “Ing-dagarna”:

- Active learning
- The professional role as an engineer
- Collaboration with industry
- Progression

According to the project members it is important to activate, motivate and engage students in order to stimulate students in their own learning process. In the development of the concept “Ing-dagar” the Kolb circle [7] and the four different ways of learning: concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract thinking and active experimentation influenced the work. For the project members, it is important to create the conditions for active learning because active learning creates motivation, interest in the subject, increases understanding of concepts and even more effective work [8]. Active participation, thus contributes to a learning outcome that corresponds to the higher levels of the SOLO taxonomy [9]. Lecturing has a tendency to result in passive listening and less effective learning compared to situations where the students are more active and engaged [10]. The project members use, for example teamwork, casework and reflections in the active learning process. Another active approach can be reached by introducing blended learning. The literature presents different definitions of blended learning and there is still no clear definition of the term according to Kuhn et al. [11]. However, a presented definition is that blended learning is a combination of different learning techniques, technologies and delivery procedures [12, 13], and another definition focuses on online teaching integrated with classroom education [14]. To integrate digital tools with classroom education has a positive impact on the students’ experience of their studies, their experienced control over their own learning, on throughput and on the achievements [15,16,17]. This is also supported by results by Parson et al. [18] showing that overall students indicate that podcasts and vodcasts were a beneficial additional resource for learning, especially used together with lecturers’ slides and when used for assessment.

One way of introducing blended learning is to use Flipped Classroom where the basic idea is to replace traditional lectures with active in-class activities and pre-/post-classwork [19]. Often the students are given an assignment before class to prepare and the time in the classroom is used for active learning under the teacher’s guidance. This is for example used in Ing 1b. When using blended learning it is important to map the teaching methods and monitor the learning. The monitoring serves three purposes; identify that the students learnt what was taught, see that students prepare for class and to identify parts where many students have problems [20]. The use of Flipped Classroom gives “better relationships, greater student engagement, and higher levels of motivation” [21]. The professional role as an engineer and collaboration with industry are also key components for the project. It is

agreed on by representatives from higher education institutions that industry related activities give pedagogical values and makes the graduates more employable [22], and collaboration seems to inspire and motivate students to work more efficiently [23]. A main concern for the project members is also to design learning activities, which encourage students to adopt an active approach to learning and also a progression over time. A “deep learning approach” described by Biggs [9] allows students to connect new knowledge to existing ideas and build an understanding. For example, create activities that increase in complexity and run as a red thread throughout the three years of education.

2 THE ORGANISATION AND CONTENT

To have ongoing themes regarding non-technical engineering skills throughout the three years of education is the idea of “Ing-dagar”. All activities such as group dynamics, ethical discussions, engineering writing are mandatory and will take place within the framework of existing courses. The activities are included in the six “Ing-dagar” presented in figure 1 and relate to six different themes, ethics, communication, the engineering profession, teamwork, entrepreneurship and international and intercultural aspects. Three of the days (Ing 0, Ing 1a and Ing 1b) are linked to courses in year one, two of the days (Ing 2a and Ing 2b) are linked to courses during spring in year two and the last day (Ing 3) to courses in the autumn in year three. Students are also given the opportunity to supplement the compulsory activities with voluntary activities and are then able to be certified in non-technical engineering competence (CITIK) and receive a diploma that can be attached to the student's CV.

Figure 1

Ing 0 is held one of the first days of the students' education and focuses on teamwork, ethics and the engineering profession. The day begins with teambuilding activities with the aim of getting the students to know each other and to encourage cooperation and social interaction among the new students. According to the theme ethics they are given a lecture on basic values, the discrimination act and master suppression techniques. The lecture is then followed by group discussions. Regarding the theme the engineering profession, the students are encouraged to bring a picture that illustrates the professional role of an engineer and/or how engineers affect society. In class they then gather in groups presenting their pictures to each other and each group agrees on one of the pictures. The selected pictures are then later presented on the day Ing 1a, where the students can vote for the “Engineering picture of the year”. The activity is intended to create discussion about what an engineer is and the students' future professional role. In order to address the role of the engineer further, films are shown where alumnus describes their work. They also provide advice to the students for their ongoing studies.

Ing 1a, with a focus on written communication is also the starting point of “Writing for engineers”, part of the introductory course. The students practice information search, reading scientific articles, writing summaries and reflections based on the articles. They also peer review each other’s text. During Ing 1a, the students are introduced to the non-technical skills included in the Ing-days and the skills are put into context and the importance of these skills for their professional life is stressed out. The activity “Writing for engineers” is also presented, and it is emphasised that writing skills are important both during the education and during a professional career as an engineer. To prepare the students for the writing assignment, experts on language and writing from The Academic Support Centre of Lund University give a lecture on good writing style and on how to write a review of an article. Many students “borrow” pictures and other material they find on the Internet without checking if it is free to use or without asking for permission. To make the students aware of the dangers of that, basic facts about intellectual property and especially about copyright is presented to the students. Traditional copyright and new concepts like Creative Commons are described. The main message is that if they are not sure that they have permission to use material they have found, they shouldn’t do it. Also, plagiarism and what it may lead to are discussed. The last part of the day focuses on group dynamics, teamwork and working in project groups, especially how to handle conflicts. This part concludes with a group exercise for the students, where they shall abolish five civic rights in a country. They get a list with civic rights and the task is to agree on what rights that should be abolished. Finally the students vote for the best engineering picture from Ing 0, and the winner receives a small prize.

Ing 1b includes ethics in the form of digital traces, teamwork and group dynamics. To randomly group the students they are given a piece of paper with a picture of a well-known person, real or fictitious. In the room there are paperboards figure picturing the persons in the pieces of paper and the students find the matching paperboard figure. There will be about five students per paperboard figure. A short lecture on digital traces is given, about the history of information acquisition by governments and companies and the possibilities of today are described and exemplified. Examples include the use of cookies in targeted advertising and how criminals have been found just by using their digital traces. The students have prepared themselves before the lecture by reading a number of articles on the subject. After the lecture the students carry out a number of tasks, 1-3 as a group and 4 as individuals:

1. They read a story about a day in the life of their figure (1-2 pages long). The group of students shall find the digital traces left by the figure during that day. Most groups find about a dozen traces.
2. They chose three of the traces and analyse them more closely. They shall answer questions like: Who collects the data? How is data used? What’s good with collecting this data? What’s bad with collecting this data? What is the worst that could happen if the data is used in a malicious way?
3. They chose one of the traces from assignment 2 and make a poster about that trace.
4. They vote for the best poster. The winning group gets a small, symbolic prize.

Ing 2a is part of project courses and therefore closely linked to teamwork, but the day also relates to ethics and intercultural aspects. After an introduction the students work in their project groups with establishing ground rules, a set of expected behaviours within the group. The ground rules and consequences for non-compliance are then documented in the

different project groups' project plan. In class the students then get a short presentation of sequential and synchronous time perception and how this differs over the world. They gather in their project groups again and discuss what affect sequential and synchronous time perception has on project plans and agreements on how to work regarding time planning and meetings in multicultural teams or with companies in other countries. The final group discussion is about the Code of Honour (The Swedish Association Of Graduate Engineers) where the students try to agree on the three most important principles. The individual assignment at the end of the project courses includes parts where the student reflects on his/her own commitment in the group, the ground rules and what activities in the project would be affected if the project members come from other countries. The individual assignment is designed as a personal letter for a job application and is a continuing training of writing skills from "Ing 1a" but focusing on another target group as well as training in applying for work. Students receive support in their writing from the Academic support centre and they also receive a guest lecture on how to write a personal letter from the Human Resources Department of a company.

Ing 2b continuous from "Ing 2a" with intercultural aspects, an invited guest lecture from a global company share experiences of working in multicultural teams, how the experience is to live and work in Sweden, differences, similarities and things to think about when working with people from other countries. After the guest lecture group discussions are held and written summarised reflections are handed in. Since many of the students will work in multicultural teams or work abroad in the future, these aspects are important to highlight during the education. Ethics is also included in "Ing 2b" through a guest lecture and group discussions about the new law General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which will affect students both as individuals and professionals.

Ing 3 will be introduced in the autumn of 2018 and will focus on the students' beginning career with career coaching, CV review, negotiation techniques and entrepreneurship. The specific activities are still at the planning stage.

3 OBSERVATIONS AND LESSONS LEARNED

The concept "Ing-dagarna" has not fully been implemented yet, Ing 0, Ing 1a and Ing 1b have been given two times, Ing 2a and Ing 2b just once and Ing 3 is in the planning phase. The activities are still changing based on observations and lesson learned. The observations and lessons learned so far will be presented in this section.

The students are introduced to written communication during Ing 1a and there are indications that the students' writing skills have improved according to statements from teachers who meet the students' writing in later courses, when they write reports, reflections and thesis. It has been noticed that the structure of the written texts and the language has improved. Coping with copyright issues, for example regarding the use of other people's pictures and figures has also improved, showing that the students take into account the ethical aspects presented in class. However, since this is a work in progress at an early stage, no systematic evaluation has been done yet. A more comprehensive evaluation of progression regarding the writing is planned in cooperation with The Academic Support Centre of Lund University.

A lesson learnt during the first year when the evaluation showed that some students did not understand the purpose of the writing activities. To address this and improve motivation, the second year the writing was put into context and it was described in detail what the students are going to write during their education and in their professional working life.

The student work in teams from the first day (Ing 0) with team building activities were the main goal for the students is to getting to know each other and start to communicate. They also start to reflect on their professional role by choosing a picture that they think illustrates the professional role of an engineer and/or how engineers affect society. The students choose a picture freely, they don't get a number of pictures to choose from. The pictures illustrate what the students think are the most important aspects of the engineering profession. The three most common aspects in decreasing order have been:

- Problem solving (many different kinds of pictures)
- Entrepreneurship and the engineer as a hero (many with a portray of Elon Musk)
- The impact of engineering on society (many different kinds of pictures)

The results for 2016 and 2017 were similar. When the students voted for the "Engineering picture of the year" during Ing 1a, a flowchart won in 2016 and the Eiffel tower in 2017. The intention is to do the same activity during Ing 3 to investigate whether the students' views on an engineer have changed during their studies.

The students further work in teams during Ing 1a with ethical aspects where the students were given 15 civil rights granted to the citizens of a fictive country. As described, the students' task, chose five rights they thought could be abolished. This has been done in 2016 and 2017, and the results were very similar. The rights most groups wanted to abolish were related to physical mobility and freedom in everyday life, for example the right to swim and camp anywhere, the right to park anywhere and the right to walk the dog anywhere. The rights most groups wanted to keep were related to communication, media and professional life for example the right to choose telephone operator freely, the right to criticize your boss without reprisals and the right not to be contacted by telemarketing companies without permission. Perhaps there is a trend that students do not chose rights related to physical activity and politics and consider the most important rights to communication and media but this is to soon to conclude.

Ethics, teamwork and group dynamics are in focus during Ing 1b and the students work in groups with finding the digital traces left by a fictitious person during the person's day. Almost all the student groups discover about a dozen traces, a very good result. The winner in the poster content was a poster about the use of cookies in 2017 and about the use and misuse of assault alarms in 2018, both very relevant traces. Most of the posters can be classified into the categories, economic transactions (paying or ordering by electronic transactions) or surveillance and tracking services. In the first category the students identifies the problems with fraud and systematically map of users in the second integrity problems. Most students seem to fear that individuals or companies can misuse information, not that authorities or the state can do it. The reason for that is probably that Swedish people usually trust the state and local authorities. The students also see the advantages of technology that leaves digital traces, so their view is quite balanced.

To get progression regarding teamwork and also include intercultural aspects, more ethics and connections to industry during the students' year two, the students work in project

groups and during Ing 2a the students discuss project plans and ground rules. The most common ground rules agreed on by the project groups are rules regarding attendance at meetings, working hours, treating each others with respect and being active and contribute to the project. The students also discuss the effect on project plans and agreements on how to work in multicultural teams or with companies in other countries. The discussions and reflections written individually later in the connected project course shows that the students were well aware about the problems that may arise and how to handle them. During Ing 2b the students are presented to intercultural aspects again from another perspective by meeting an invited guest lecture from a global company sharing experiences of working in multicultural teams, and work in Sweden when you come from another country. After the lecture the students discuss in groups and a written reflections are handed in. A summary of the reflections shows that the main lessons for the students are that people are not 0:s or 1:s, there is a endless spectrum of personalities, there is always something that people have in common, what I look like does not define who I am, we have prejudices we are not aware of, it is important with respect and understanding, and business cultures differ between countries.

At first we had concerns that the students would not perceive "Ing-dagarna" to be interesting, but experiencing the different subjects as "dopey", but based on teachers' observations during the "Ing-dagarna", it seems to be the opposite. The students are interested and engage in the various tasks. Based on previous experience of using external resources that worked with students in for example group dynamics, we have avoided external resources because the students responded negatively. They experienced the activities as diffuse and irrelevant. This has led us to link the activities explicitly to current courses, and for example ethical aspects are related to contexts like digital traces.

4 FUTURE WORK

To complete the concept "Ing-dagarna", the last building block in the concept Ing 3 will be launched during autumn 2018.

Since this is an ongoing work, the students have evaluated different parts separately, such as guest lectures and written communication, never the entire "Ing-dagar" concept. The students have been mostly positive in their evaluations. However, the whole concept will be continuously evaluated and updated. The objective is to develop an overall plan for systematic evaluation and data collection in order to be able to follow the various activities over time and get more feedback from the students.

To make the students even more active during "Ing-dagarna", concepts and tools for blended learning will be introduced. Digital tools will be used where it is appropriate. The use of Flipped classroom will be further developed. Today it is used in conjunction with Ing 1 b where the students prepare by reading articles, but this need to be developed further.

We in the group who are developing and working with "Ing-dagarna", experience that we get to know our students better, and they contact us also regarding other matters. We as a group have strengthened our collaboration, we have become better at utilize each other's skills and strengths and our goal is to maintain this and further develop.

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